

Determination of trace metal contents of tobacco in different brands of cigarettes – a valuable tool in forensic investigation and criminology

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Abstract : Tobacco leaves used in cigarettes for smoking contain various toxic trace elements. These are expected to be absorbed in human body relatively in excess and may exceed toxic limits due to repeated uses of cigarettes through years. Trace metal contents like cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, lead, cadmium, arsenic and mercury were determined quantitatively for tobacco in different brands of Indian cigarettes. They may not be health hazards at low concentrations but the cumulative effects for years of frequent cigarette smoking may prove to be fatal.

Metal contents in cigarettes may be used to differentiate and establish the smuggled or counterfeit origin of cigarettes but it is a relatively less used tool of potential interest from the point of view of forensic investigation and criminology.

Keywords : Counterfeit cigarettes, criminology, health hazards, metal contents, tobacco leaves, toxic elements.

Introduction

It is well known that all natural products contain macro and micro nutrients in varying proportions. A limited amount of micronutrients like Cu, Zn, Ni, Pb, Cd, Hg, Fe are required for the metabolic growth and enzyme activities of animal and human world^{1,2} but higher concentrations are toxic to the plant and other living systems. Though it is very difficult to prescribe safe limits for the consumption of metal ions for the body system but limits for the concentrations of the same ions have been tentatively prescribed as a guide³.

Tobacco plant (*Nicotinia tabacum*) absorbs different macro and micro (trace) elements from soil and the elements are distributed in different parts of the body including leaves and they are concentrated in the leaves. The presence and concentration level of metal in plants like tobacco are influenced by facts like genotype, soil type, soil pH, fertilizers, pesticides etc.⁴⁻⁶.

Metal contents in cigarettes and cigarette ashes/smoke are usually determined in tobacco of the cigarettes (blended cigarettes with various other products added during blending and cigarette elaboration). Extensive works related to the determination of different metals in tobacco leaves,

cigarettes, cigarette smokes and ashes, smokeless tobacco products have been made and works has been going on⁷⁻¹². The main goal or interest in the works is to establish the toxicity or health risks and the possible hazardous effects on the environment. Metal content has also been used to establish the smuggled/counterfeit origin of cigarettes^{7,13,14}. This is a topic of potential interest from the point of view of forensics and criminology. However, works in this direction are few. Arther Conan Doyle¹⁵, one of the architects of forensic criminology examined 140 different varieties of pipes, cigars and cigarettes to unveil and explain crime mysteries. Systemic investigation of the metal toxicity of the different brands of cigarettes is thus desirable. The controversial aspect of metal toxicity led us to examine the metal contents like Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Pb, Hg, As in a few brands of Indian cigarettes purchased from the local market which is presented in this paper.

Experimental^{9,13}

Different brands of Indian cigarettes (with their average weight and average tobacco contents per cigarette) as presented in Table 1 were the experimental samples. The chemical used were all of AnalaR quality from E. Merck.

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Table 1. Different brands of Indian cigarettes (with their average weight and average tobacco contents per cigarette)

Code	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Name of the brand	Gold Flake Honey Dew (Filter Tipped) Cig. length : 69 mm	Gold Flake Honey Dew Smooth Kings (Filter Tipped) Cig. length : 84 mm	Wills Navy Cut (Filter Tipped) Cig. length : 74 mm	Wills Navy Cut (Regular Size) Cig. length : 69 mm	Wills Silk Cut Cig. length : 69 mm	Wills Flake Filter Cig. length : 69 mm	Special (Filter) Cig. length : 69 mm
Average wt. of each cigarette (g)	0.8194	0.9435	0.8888	0.8029	0.8084	0.8035	0.8328
Average content of tobacco/cigarette (g)	0.6585	0.7061	0.7244	0.6422	0.6505	0.6448	0.6961

About 2 g of each brand of cigarettes was initially utilised for each experiment. Powdered tobacco was taken in a silica crucible and heated at 450 °C for 3 h or until completely ashed. The ashed material was gently heated with 5 mL of aqua regia to complete dryness. Again 10 mL of 6 M HCl was added and the acid was evaporated slowly by careful heating in a hot plate. Finally, the residue was dissolved in 0.5 N HNO₃ and transferred by filtration by Whatmann 42 filter paper in a 50 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark. For analysis of As the residue was dissolved in 2 N HCl solution.

The metal contents (namely Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) were measured using Varian Fast Sequential Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (model AA 240 FS).

The same instrument coupled with Vapour Generation assembly VGA 77 was used for As measurement. Before analysis the solution was reduced using 1% KI and 0.5% ascorbic acid solution. 1 : 1 HCl and 0.6% NaBH₄ were used to convert As into AsH₃.

Cd and Pb were measured using Varian Zeeman Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (model AA 240Z) coupled with Graphite Tube Atomizer GTA 120.

For analysis of Hg, 0.2 g of sample was directly analysed using Direct Mercury Analyser (DMA-80) of M/S Milestone Srl.

The parameters for instrumental measurements are given in Tables 2–4. Calibrations of the instruments were made using multi-traceable standards from NIST with 3 different standard solutions for each metal ion.

Table 2. Analytical parameters of Direct Mercury Analyser (DMA-80)

Parameter	Values
AAS-System	Single beam
Drying temperature	200 °C for solid samples
Decomposition programme	Initial 25 °C ramped to 200 °C (hold 1 min) at 350 °C/min increment, again ramped to 650 °C (hold for 3 min) at 300 °C/min increment
Decomposition temperature	650 °C
Catalytic reduction temperature	615 °C
Amalgamation temperature	170 °C
De-mercurisation temperature	900 °C
Carrier gas	Oxygen
Ground state Hg formation temperature	125 °C
Purity of oxygen gas	99.99%
Flow rate of oxygen gas	160–200 ml/min
Gas pressure	4.0 bar
Light source	Low pressure Hg vapour lamp
Wave length of light source	253.65 nm
Detector	Silicon UV diode
Working range	Up to 600 µg/kg of Hg
Composition of amalgamator	3% Gold and silicate materials
Composition of reductive catalyst	A mixture of Co and Mn oxides with KOH

Table 3. Analytical parameters for analysis of Pb and Cd by AAS-GTA

Parameter	Pb	Cd
Mode	Auto mix	Auto mix
Measurement	Peak height	Peak height
Lamp current (mA)	5.0	4.0
Wavelength (nm)	283.3	228.8

Table-3 (contd.)

Slit width (nm)	0.5	0.5
Background correction	Zeeman	Zeeman
Modifier	0.5% ADP in ultrapure water	None
Sample volume (μL)	10	10
Modifier volume (μL)	5	0
Blank (0.5% HNO ₃) volume (μL)	0	5
Bulk concentration of standard solution (μg/L)	50	10
Standard for making calibration curve (μg/L)	10, 20, 30	2, 4, 6
Reslope rate	10	10
Recalibration rate	20	20

N.B. : ADP = Amonium di-hydrogen phosphate.

Table 4. Analytical parameters for analysis of Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and As by flame AAS

Parameter	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	As
Wavelength (nm)	240.7	232.0	324.0	213.9	193.7
Flame type	Air/Acetylene				
Slit width (nm)	0.2	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.5
Lamp current (mA)	7.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	10
Calibration soln.	1.25, 2.5, 5 (mg/L)	1.5, 3, 6 (mg/L)	1, 2, 4 (mg/L)	0.2, 0.4, 0.8 (mg/L)	5, 10, 20, 40 (μg/L)

Results and discussion

The concentrations of metal ions in different brands of cigarettes are presented in Table 5. LOQ (lowest limit of quantitation) for the estimation of metal ions are also given in the table.

It is seen that the concentrations of metal ions can be regarded to be moderate to high. However, these are present in tobacco of different brands of cigarettes and cannot be regarded to be absorbed in the body system. In the smoking process, the metal contents are expected to remain in the ashes and to some extent in the mainstream and side stream smoke, i.e. they pollute the air or environment. The ash content may vary from smoker to smoker. The ash contents can be obtained if the cigarettes were subjected to a smoke procedure with a smoking machine using the standard smoking parameters or habits of human beings. Therefore, metal ions consumed by the body system are metal ions determined in tobacco leaves minus metal ions present in the ashes or slightly

Table 5. The concentrations of metal ions in different brands of cigarettes

Code of the brand	Average values of metal ions mg/kg and μg/kg (for Hg and As)							
	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb	Hg	As
A	1.48	2.66	8.38	11.53	0.24	1.35	5.74	64.63
B	1.53	2.88	7.70	11.86	0.16	1.22	10.90	40.61
C	1.34	2.49	8.34	11.95	0.31	2.06	8.16	61.83
D	1.55	2.70	7.48	11.03	0.35	0.87	12.11	44.93
E	1.87	2.85	8.37	11.04	0.51	2.37	5.29	36.60
F	1.76	3.53	7.88	11.94	0.30	4.15	5.85	47.36
G	1.21	3.93	7.18	12.04	0.40	3.22	7.51	32.91
LOQ (μg/kg)	3	1.5	9	3	0.3	5	0.4	0.2

LOQ = $a + 10b$, where a is the average value of the processed blank solution ($n > 10$), b is the standard deviation of the measurements.

less due to environmental distribution. Metal concentrations in cigarettes may be low and are not hazardous but cumulative effects of frequent use of cigarettes over the years are definitely health hazards due to increased accumulation of toxic metals in the body system.

Moreover, metal ions may be absorbed due to air, water and particularly from soil pollution. Air, water and soil are contaminated from :

- (i) Burning of fossil fuels and other secondary effects,
- (ii) Contamination due to discharge of industrial (including power houses and mining process), municipal and domestic effluents,
- (iii) Metallic contamination in fertilizers, pesticides and therapeutic agents, to name a few.

Soil contaminations have far reaching influences as many of the contaminants are absorbed by the body system through the food chain i.e. vegetables, fruits, rice, cereals etc. the effects of bioamplification and biomagnifications mean increased concentrations of those contaminants including metal ions from meat, fish etc.³.

Therefore, it is difficult to predict positively the effects of metal ions in our body system from tobacco smoke or smokeless tobacco but smoking or using smokeless tobacco can be avoided.

However, metal contents of the tobaccos (preferably in the ashes) can be utilised in discriminating the different

brands of tobacco and for the possibility of developing classification models to differentiate different brands of cigarettes and their origin⁷. It provides a way to identify counterfeit origin of cigarettes¹³⁻¹⁵. Metal contents in the ashes of cigarettes may be utilised in forensic investigation and criminology.

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